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Educators' Characteristics and Application of Emerging Technologies in Teacher Education

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ABSTRACT

The study was an investigation into educator's characteristics and application of emerging technologies in teacher education. The study was carried out in Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education Owerri, Imo State. Based on the objectives of the study, two research questions and a hypothesis guided the study. The descriptive survey research design was adopted in carrying out the study. The sample for the study consists of 250 educators selected through stratified random sampling technique. The data required for the study was collected using researchers made likert 4-points type questionnaire titled "Educators Characteristics and Application of Emerging Technologies in Teacher Education (ECAETTE)". The instrument had reliability coefficient of 0.75 determined using Cronbach's alpha formula. The data generated were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions, while the hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistical tool. The result of the study revealed that, the application of emerging technologies depends on educator's characteristics such as years of teaching experience, age, digital competence, and others. There was no significant difference between the response means of male and female educators based on their characteristics and application of emerging technologies in teacher education. Based on the result, it was recommended among other things that, conferences, workshops and seminars be organized to improve educator's knowledge on application of emerging technologies in teacher education.

Keywords: Educators, Characteristics, Emerging Technologies,

INTRODUCTION

The evolution of technologies in the 21st century, has revolutionized the entire world and brought about paradigm shift in the teaching and learning experiences. The innovation brought by these technologies has kept transforming traditional pedagogical practice, which before now, was a setback to the socio-economic, scientific and technological advancement of developing Nations. The integration of emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Virtual Reality (VR), and Augmented Reality (AR), into the classrooms has redirected teaching and learning towards acquiring basic skills which include critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, communication, innovation and problem solving. The use of these technologies in teaching and learning has also re-designed the way educators present information and engage students, leading to more effective and immersive learning experiences. Ibrahim (2024) reported

that, in the rapidly changing field of education, incorporating emerging technologies into teacher preparation has become a crucial way to promote global competitiveness.

Emerging technologies (ET) are defined as innovative advancements that have the potential to create new industries or transform existing ones. These technologies are characterized by their ability to enhance processes, improve efficiency, and provide novel solutions across various fields, including Education, healthcare, information management, and environmental sustainability. Emerging technologies are innovative scientific and technological advancements that exhibit unique characteristics, influencing various economic sectors and necessitating new methodologies for their study and application. Oforma and Bassey (2021) stated that, emerging technology include the internet back-bone as well as other electronic media devices and facilities that ensure E-learning. Such as broadband desktop, laptop, tablets, smartphones and other hand-held devices, wide range of electronic technology devices such as radio, cassette tapes, audio streams, downloadable packages, internet services, television, Ipad, interactive boards etc. Sembey et al. (2024) defined emerging technologies in education as innovative tools like Artificial Intelligence, Learning Analytics, and Extended Reality that enhance teaching, learning, assessment, and feedback practices in higher education. Ukonu (2020) posited that emerging technologies are electronic devices ploughed into the educational enterprise which involves compute- based classroom interactions, video conferencing, zoom e-mail and entire social media applications. In the idea of Eimuhi and Aiwuyo (2022) emerging technologies are set out to modify teaching/learning efficacy as it is very accommodating, fosters exploration, promotes positive teaching/learning outcomes among students and enhances teachers' job performances to a desirable level. Similarly, Onyema (2019) recognized emerging technologies as synonymous with Information Computer Technology (ICT) by describing the ICT as an essential tool in teaching/learning situations which has unlocked the key of digitalizing classroom facilities.

The pedagogical transformation brought about by emerging technologies in the 21st century has led to unlimited access to learning resources both within and outside the classroom environment enabling uninterrupted learning opportunities among learners. The use of technology as a support in education makes it flexible and stimulating for students, because they acquire skills such as spatial visualization, innovative thinking, problem solving, analytical and critical thinking (Zongo, 2014). The application of emerging technologies has become so irresistible in the teaching and learning process, and it is changing the way teaching is structured and organized, and the job performance of educators. The adoption and usage of emerging technologies assist educators and students to interact more outside the classroom, and to set up classes at any time and place (Onyema, 2020).

Teacher education is designed to prepare would be teachers on the business of becoming professional teachers as such, the acquisition of technological skills should be paramount in their training process in other to be relevant in the 21st century education demands. Teachers play an important role in the teaching and learning paradigm shift. They must understand the potential role of technology in education. Also, they should become effective agents to be able to make use of technology in the classroom (Afshari et al, 2009). Ukoha cited in Morma and Bassey (2021) opined that if education has to do with teaching, curriculum and setting, then teacher education has to do with creating an enabling environment so that someone can impart through different ways appropriate knowledge and skills to someone who is willing to be a teacher, or someone who is already a teacher but wishes to enhance his/her capacity in discharging those teaching functions effectively. The digital culture of the 21st century demands that every professional teacher should be conversant with the application of technologies in the teaching and learning process which has become part of the students. Trembach and Deng (2018) stated that ETs applied to education have become a valuable learning resource because they motivate students to develop competitive skills to meet the job needs of the present and the future. Law et al. (2005) opined that innovation in education allows students to effectively use digital technologies to generate, transform, discuss, collaborate, collect, and disseminate criteria, enabling the evolution of knowledge. Emerging technologies not only refocus teaching and learning, it also prepares the students to be meaningful in the

society through becoming problem solvers. ETs help in the development of entrepreneurship skills of students which is very essential in today's society. Incorporating technologies in teacher education enhances students' interest and engagement by incorporating gamification, virtual field trips, and online resources. It also encourages active participation, a challenge in traditional lecture environments. It enhances knowledge retention, as it encourages active classroom participation. Application of technology in the classroom enhances learning by allowing students to learn at their own pace. It caters for struggling or disabled students, providing diverse research resources and increased engagement. Students' collaborative skills are enhanced through online activities like project sharing and virtual learning environments, fostering connections across classrooms, schools, and globally. It enhances teaching by providing online resources like virtual lesson plans, grading software, and assessments. Parry and Battista (2019) stated that technologies, such as Artificial Intelligence and robotics, are being employed by organizations to automate simple and repetitive tasks as well as to make complex decisions quick and more accurate but it also present a number of challenges for HR professionals who will need to help employees to update their skills to compete in the future world of work. Patrick (2018) stated that emerging technologies revolutionize the way students and teachers work and interact and try to make learning more efficient, engaging and entertaining thereby attracting both the students and the universities that enroll them. In the words of Corinne (2018) emerging technologies have spawned the exponential development of software and AI-aided, cloud-based technology that aim to adapt learning methods and customize curricula to fit each student's ability to move forward at his or her own pace.

Irrespective of the enormous roles played by emerging technologies in the development of education in the 21st century, educators are still skeptical in its application in teacher education. The successful integration of technologies and benefits associated with it in teacher education seriously depends on the disposition of the educators. Nwoke et al (2020) reported that although the use of technological facilities in teaching and learning have become inevitable to produce marketable and employable graduates, many teacher training institutions in Nigeria suffer from a lack of application or use of appropriate technologies by lecturers. This may stem from their lack of competence in the application of technological tools in teaching and learning process because educators who are competent in the use of technologies for personal purpose utilize them in classroom situation than those who are not competent. Ifinedo et al. (2020) in a study reported that technical knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and technology integration knowledge can also directly influence teachers' ICT integration, while teachers' gender, age, years of teaching experience, and class size can also significantly influence ICT use. Pelila et al. (2022) reported that elements that significantly influence how effectively technology is integrated into teaching practices by educators include personal perspectives and attitudes, professional aspects such as tenure, training, and workshops. These elements significantly influence how effectively technology is integrated into teaching practices. Khan et al. (2017) stated that factors influencing technology use in the classroom include gender, age, cultural background, teaching experience, and individual feelings such as anxiety and competence. These factors significantly affect educators' decisions regarding the integration of educational technologies into their pedagogical strategies. In the same vein Ching and Kwok (2022) indicated that factors determining the use of technology in the classroom include attitude toward usage (ATU), perceived usefulness (PU), perceived ease of use (PEU), subjective norm (SN), and facilitating conditions (FC), which collectively explain 65.3% of the variance in intention to use. Afshari et al. (2009) reported that personal characteristics of teachers are an important influence on how easily they take up an innovation. Ibrahim (2024) reported that, acknowledging and proactively engaging with these challenges, the education community can foster an environment conducive to the successful incorporation of emerging technologies into teacher education programs, ultimately contributing to global competitiveness.

It may be effort in futility if the teacher education is not practically approached, positioned and engaged through availability, accessibility and competency in the emerging technologies. Teacher Education

programmes should be structured to equip teachers for effective performance of their duties (Morina & Bassey, 2021).

The research reports reviewed are evidence of the integration of emerging technologies in education in other lands and fields. However, there are no convincing evidence of the application of emerging technologies in teacher education within geographical zone of this study. Therefore, the current study was carried out to determine Educators' Characteristics and Application of Emerging Technologies in Teacher Education

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine educators' characteristics and application of emerging technologies in teacher education. Specifically, the study will determine;

- 1). Educators' characteristics that determine their application of emerging technologies in teacher education
- 2). Whether educators' characteristics and application of emerging technologies in teacher education is dependent on gender.
- 3). The relationship between educators' characteristics and application of emerging technologies in teacher education.

Research Questions

The following research question were addressed in the study

- 1). What are the educators' characteristics that determine application of emerging technologies in teacher education?
- 2). What is the difference between the response means of male and female educators on their characteristics and application of emerging technologies in teacher education?

Hypothesis

The study was guided by a hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between response means of male and female educators on their characteristics and application of emerging technologies in teacher education.

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study to investigate educators' characteristics and application of emerging technologies in teacher education. The population consisted of seven hundred and twenty-two (722) educators of Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education Owerri in Imo State, Nigeria. A sample of two hundred and fifty (250) educators from seven (7) faculties of the University was selected for the study through stratified random sampling technique. This consists of 130 females and 120 males. The instrument for data collection was researchers made 13-items Likert type questionnaire titled "Educators' Characteristics and Application of Emerging Technologies in Teacher Education (ECAETTE)". The instrument had two sections A and B. Section A was about the respondents' variables, while section B dealt with items related to the objectives of the study. The responses ranged as Strongly Agree (SA), Agreed (A), Disagree(D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The instrument was validated by 2 experts in measurement and evaluation and a teacher education expert from the University. A pilot study of the instrument was carried out using Educators from a College of Education within Imo state of Nigeria, a reliability coefficient of 0.75 was determined through Cronbach's alpha formula, this was adjudged suitable for the study. The instrument was administered to the respondents on a face-to-face basis which lasted for a week and all the instruments were recovered. The data generated were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions. Response means within and above the criterion mean of 2.50 were accepted, while any below the criterion mean was rejected. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistical tool.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What are the educators' characteristics that determine application of emerging technologies in teacher education?*

Table 1: Summary of responses on educators' characteristics that determine application of emerging technologies

S/N	Item	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Digital competence determines educators' application of emerging technologies in teaching and learning	3.63	0.72	Accept
2	Educators gender affects application of emerging technologies in teaching and learning	2.20	0.85	Reject
3	Level of qualification is a factor in application of emerging technologies	3.31	1.03	Accept
4	Years of experience affects educators' application of emerging technologies	3.33	1.02	Accept
5	Attitude towards technology affects application of emerging technologies.	3.21	1.00	Accept
6	Educators' self-efficacy determines their application of emerging technologies	2.85	1.27	Accept
7	Educators level of professional development affects application of emerging technologies	3.11	1.03	Accept
8	Course content knowledge determines educator application of emerging technologies.	2.61	1.20	Accept
9	Educators personal experience can determine application of emerging technologies.	2.57	1.24	Accept
10	Resistant to change affects educators' application of emerging technologies	2.52	1.23	Accept
11	Educators age affects the application of emerging technologies in teaching and learning.	3.21	0.97	Accept
12	Educators' Financial status affects application of emerging technologies in teaching and learning.	2.71	0.93	Accept
13	Educators teaching style determines application of emerging technologies	2.63	1.20	Accept
Average Mean		2.92	0.98	

Table 1 shows that all items except item 2 were accepted as they had response means greater than the criterion mean. Item 2 was rejected as it had response mean less than the criterion mean. Also, the average mean of 2.92 is greater than the criterion mean.

Research Question 2: *What is the difference between the response means of male and female educators on the characteristics that determine application of emerging technologies in teacher education?*

Table 2: Summary of mean responses of Male and female educators

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Mean diff	df	t-cal	t-0.05	Remark
Male	120	3.02	0.97	0.07	248	0.583	1.65	NS
Female	130	2.95	0.94					

Table 2 shows that, male educators had response mean of 3.02 with a standard deviation of 0.97. Their female counterparts had response mean of 2.95 with standard deviation of 0.94. These gave a difference in response in mean of 0.07 in favour of male educators.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between response means of male and female educators on their characteristics and application of emerging technologies in teacher education.

Table 2 indicates that, the t-calculated value of 0.583 is less than the table value of 1.65 at degree of freedom 248 and 0.05 level of significance. Based on the result, the null hypothesis is upheld. This implies that, there is no significant difference between the response means of male and female educators on their characteristics and application of emerging technologies in teacher education.

DISCUSSION

The result of the study indicated that in table 1, items 1 and 3-13 were accepted as they had response means greater than the criterion mean. The result implies that, digital competence, level of qualification,

age, self-efficacy, years of experience, attitude towards technology, professional development, course content knowledge, personal experience, resistant to change, financial status and teaching style are educators' characteristics that affects application of emerging technologies in teacher education. Also, item 2 was rejected as it had response mean less than the criterion mean. This was an indication that, educators' gender does not affect the application of emerging technologies in teacher education. Further analysis revealed no statistically significant difference between the response means of male and female respondents on educators' characteristics and application of emerging technologies in teacher education. This implies that their responses were not gender dependent. This result is related with Ifinedo et al. (2020), Albirini (2006), Afshari et al (2009), Drent and Meelissen (2007), Pelila et al. (2022), Khan et al. (2017) and Ibrahim (2024) who variously identified attitude towards technology, training program on technology usage, digital competence, teaching experience, teachers age, exposure to technologies resistance to change as teacher factors influencing use of technologies in the classroom.

CONCLUSION

The result of study revealed that digital competence, level of qualification, age, self-efficacy, years of experience, attitude towards technology, professional development, course content knowledge, personal experience, resistant to change, financial status and teaching style are educators' characteristics that affect application of emerging technologies in teacher education and gender has no influence on it.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that;

- 1). The Government and Management of tertiary institutions should organize, conferences, workshops and seminars to train and retrain educators on application of emerging technologies in teacher education.
- 2). Government should make available technological facilities in teacher training institutions to enable educators apply them in teaching and learning.
- 3). The Government should support educators financially to purchase digital tools to enhance their competence and apply them appropriately in teacher education.

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